

A Comparative Study HR Practices between Public & Private Bank in Pakistan

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Abstract

The main Purpose of this study is to examine the relationship and nature of relationship between the employee perceived performance and human resource (HR) practices (planning, training compensation, performance appraisal, and selection & Recruitment) in the banking sector of Pakistan. Analysis of 100 banking employees was conducted through personally administrated questionnaire to investigate the impact of HR practices on employees' perceived performance. The relationship and nature of relationship is calculated by applying the Box Plot Diagrams. Results validate that, the employee perceived performance and HR practices has the positive and significant relationship. The Box Plot Diagram results indicate that the two HR practices: performance appraisal and compensation practices are considered more important in Private Banks as compared to Government Banks. Moreover, this study provides help for top-management of banking sector to design or revise their HR policies and make practices to attain high employee performance.

Keywords: Comparative study, Public and Private Bank, Pakistan, HR practices.

Introduction

Performance of any organization largely depends on the performance of its employees. Successful organizations were increasingly realizing that there were number of factors that contribute to performance but human resource was clearly the most critical (Mello, 2005). In spite of the size and nature of an organization, the activity it undertakes, and the environment in which it operates, its success depends on its employees' decisions and their behaviour. To evaluate performance of employees in organization was one of the major purposes of employing human resource practices. In the competitive environment of modern era organizations were consistently improving performance of their employees by improving HR practices. Caliskan (2010) acknowledge that HR practices were one main source of competitive advantage. Many researchers have proven that HR practices have a significant and positive relationship with employees' performance (Delery and Doty, 1996; Guest, 2002; Harley, 2002; Huselid, 1995; Qureshi et al., 2006; Tessema and Soeters, 2006). From last two decades, focusing on HR practices has been an imperative and decisivewerea for organizational performance. Effective HR practices improve the performance of organization and lead to higher profits. Datta et al. (2003) found that best use of HR practices reveals a stronger association with efficiency of firm. Human resource management (HRM) practices have significant association with accounting profits of banks (Delery and Doty, 1996).

Pakistan was an under researched country (Aycan et al., 2000). In Pakistan, little research has been done to explore the association between HR practices and employee performance in banking sector. Banking sector of Pakistan was playing basic role in the development of country's economy. Modern banking system was necessary to deal with the needs of such a developing country (Zaidi, 2005). From last five years, growth and turn around in Pakistan's banking sector has been incredible and classified as best performing sector of Pakistan (Akhtar, 2007).

The objective of this study was to examine the difference between HR practices and employees perceived performance in banking sector of Pakistan. However there were number of factors which affect employee's performance but current study focus on the relationship between two HR practices (performance evaluation, compensation and promotion practices) .Hence, findings and results of this study will help the banking sector to improve or revise their strategies for HR practices. The remaining paper was prepared as follows: literature review, data and methodology of paper, empirical results of the study and the conclusions of this study.

There were many banks which were operating in Pakistan but **National Bank of Pakistan** and **The Bank of Punjab** were taken for research as a Government Banks and on the other hand, **Habib Metro Bank Ltd** and **Summit Bank Ltd** were taken for research as a Private Banks. National Bank of Pakistan, the Bank of Punjab, Habib Metropolitan Bank Limited, Summit Bank Limited

1949 National Bank of Pakistan (NBP) was established under the National Bank of Pakistan Ordinance of 1949 and was government-owned. NBP acted as an agent of the central bank. The bank was established in 1989, pursuant to The Bank of Punjab Act 1989, and was given the status of a retail bank in 1994. The bank was established in 1989, pursuant to The Bank of Punjab was founded by Tajammal Hussain and it functions as a scheduled commercial bank, with a network of 324 branches in major business centres throughout the country.

Habib Metropolitan Bank was incorporated in Pakistan as a Public Listed Company in 1992 under the name, Metropolitan Bank Limited. The Bank commenced, duly licensed, full scheduled commercial-banking operations in October 1992. Metropolitan Bank, from October 1992 to September 2006, remained, providing its nationwide 51-branch on-line network, established as a provider of trade finance services. On October 26, 2006, Habib Bank AG Zurich's Pakistan Operations merged into Metropolitan Bank Limited and the merged entity was named Habib Metropolitan Bank Limited (HMB). HBZ was the principal shareholder of HMB.

Summit Bank Ltd was one of the fastest growing commercial banks of Pakistan, which, in a very short span of time, has expanded its network across the country and built an infrastructure based on state of the art "Risk Management Framework" as well as "IT platform." Also targeting to be a universal bank in terms of providing products and services in all key segments of banking i.e. Corporate and Investment Banking, Trade Finance, Commercial Mid-Market / SMEs, and Consumer Banking, it commenced its operations in August 2006.

The purpose of the research was to demonstrate the difference between the employee apparent performance and Human Resource (HR) practices in banking sector of Pakistan. The research I'm conducting was important because I have to find out that what were the practices of Human Resource Department of Private & Public Limited commercial Banks in Pakistan? Employees were the backbone of every organization which leads the organization on the upper level of success. If Human Resource makes good practices in favor of employees i.e.

(compensation, performance, evaluation & promotion practices) will be more beneficial for the employees of the organization. Through this research, I will provide assistance to the top level management and especially to Human Resource department of banking sector to plan or modify their HR policies.

1: What was the difference of HR practices between Public & Private Commercial Banks & their employee's performance?

2: What were the basic HR practices in public & private commercial banks?

3: How can we avoid the problems among the employees on performance basis?

H1: HR practices in public banks were not valuable according to employee's performance.

This study will be constructive study for the management of banks because there was huge difference of HR practices between Commercial Banks & Private Banks and its effects on employee's performance & satisfaction level. After this research we will also come to know that was the reason of employee's satisfaction & dissatisfaction in public & private bank.

The study will be beneficial for an organization in certain ways such as:

- It will explore the reasons behind the employee's satisfaction & dissatisfaction in Public & Private Banks.

- It will help the management to understand the employees behavior and other was sues like compensation, performance, evaluation & promotion practices

After this research, the management will be able to make strategies to solve the wassues of employees.

Absar, Zahed Husain, Balasundaram, Moniruzzaman, (2010) worked on comparative analysis of compensation practices between public and private sector. The objective of the study was to explore the differences between public and private sector industrial enterprises with respect to overall status of compensation practices. The methodology of the article includes sixty banks in which twenty six were public and thirty four private industrial enterprises. They also used questionnaire and SPSS software to analyze the data. The result of the article shows that the overall status of compensation practices of private sector was significantly better than that of public sector.

Shabana, Zafar Iqbal, the study attempt to evaluate adoptability of private sector HRM practices in public enterprises in Pakistan through a case study analysis of Sui Northern Gas Pipeline Limited (SNGPL). The basic objective of the study was to analyze the HRM practices between public and private sector. The methodology includes seventeen in-depth interviews both inside and outside HR department. Data was analyzed and technique of triangulation of data was used. The research study explores the change from traditional personnel management practices to HRM practices was observed such as variable pay, objective performance evaluation, performance-based incentives, performance-based promotion instead of tradition practices of equal pay and allowances for equal grade, experience based increments and seniority-based promotion.

Nurul Absar, Monowar, (2011) this study explored adoption of new HRM practices in the public and private sector organizations of Bangladesh. They collected data from sixty industrial enterprises through questionnaire located in the main industrial city of country, i.e. Chittagong. The methodology includes that the collected data was run through SPSS software & One-sample *t*-test for the overall status of adoption of new HRM practices in the public sector The study revealed

significant difference on adoption of new HRM practices between public and private sector industrial enterprises of Bangladesh. Employees in the private sector organizations appeared to be more satisfied than public sector organizations with organizational HRM practices.

Abdalkrim, (2012) through this study, the author examined the impact of human resource practices on organizational performance in banking sector in Saudi Arabia. The study focuses on seven variables of human resource management practices which were training&development, performance appraisal, empowerment, compensation, job rotation, participation in decision making, and selecting system. The main objective of this research was to evaluate the impact of HRM practices on organizational performance. More precisely on banking sector in Saudi Arabia. The data instrument used for data collection was questionnaire, to analyse the effect of these seven variables, using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis in order to analyse the data. The result confirm that all seven variables of HRM practices were positively correlated with organizational performance in banking sector in Saudi Arabia which indicates that the enhancement in those HR practices can lead to improvement of performance in banking sector in Saudi Arabia.

NurulAbsar, Tahlil, Balasundaram, Sadia, (2010) they worked on exploring the impact of HR practices on job satisfaction. The Authors study aims at exploring the impact of HR practices on job satisfaction in the context of Bangladesh. The sample consisted of 60 responses from 20 manufacturing firms were collected and analysed objectively. They also used hypothetical test to test the data. It was found that HR practices have significant association with job satisfaction (JS). In addition, human resource planning (HRP), and training and development (TND) were found to have positive impact on job satisfaction (JS). It was also found that T&D has the greatest impact on JS.

SaeedAkhtar, Shehzad, (2012) the Authors want to explore that how Human Resource Practices helps in implementing the organization's policies in Public sector. The purpose of the present study was to develop a research scale to assess the effective implementation of HRPs in General Public Sector Universities (GPSUs) of Pakistan. The six factors of HRPs namely recruitment and selection; orientation, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation and benefits, and working environment were used in research. Thirty four statements were selected as samples after interviewing 250 faculty members of universities. The collected data was tested and positive correlation was found which shows that all factors contribute towards assessing the main construct while relatively weaker inter-factor correlations indicate mutual independence of each factor.

Javed, Rafiq, Maqsood, Mustajab, (2012) the Authors in this study want to analyse the Impact of HR Practices on Employee Job Satisfaction in Public Sector Organizations of Pakistan. The main object of the study was to observe the relationship between three HR Practices i.e. (Training and Development, Rewards, Recognition) and the employee job satisfaction in the public sector organizations. The authors used correlation and regression in order to find the relationship between two variables: I-e dependent and independent variables. The result shows that appreciation and Training & Development (T&D) plays an important role in job satisfaction in public sector organizations of Pakistan but rewards was not having significant role in employee's job satisfaction.

NurulAbsar, Balasundaram, Kader Jilani, (2010) the problem statement on which the study was conducted was how HR practices having impact on organizational performance in

Bangladesh. The study was conducted in order fill this gap and find out the solution of it. All factors of HR practices I-e Training and Development, Rewards, Performance appraisal, were considered in this research. The data was collected from fifty manufacturing firms of Bangladesh. The sampling technique was used (50 questionnaire out of 85 were useable) and correlation & regression was used in order to find out the relation between two variables I-e Dependent and independent variables. The result shows that performance appraisal plays an important role in organizational performance.

KomalBhatti, TahirQureshi, (2007) the basic objective of the study was to how employee's participation in work having impact on job satisfaction, employee commitment and employee productivity. This study finds out the relation between employee's participation and job satisfaction, employee commitment and employee productivity. For this study, 34 organizations were contacted and only 15 responses were useable. Oil and gas, Banking and Telecommunication sectors were contacted. Conclusion of the study was Increasing employee participation will have a positive effect on employee's job satisfaction, employee commitment and employee productivity.

Richard Gbolahan, (2010) carried out the study to examine the impact of HRM practices on organizational performance in Nigeria. For study purpose, 50 samples of questionnaire were drawn into bank and 35 responses were returned. The methodology includes using of different tools to analyse the data such as Chi-square and performance of employees were also analysed through a detailed analysis of financial statement and selected HR Metrics. Study result shows through Chi-Square that there was positive association of HRM practices with organizational performance. The study recommends that Ecobank should consolidate on its well-expressed HRM policies and to ensure some improvement in its Practices.

Abeysekera, (2007) this study empirically evaluated six Human Resource (HR) practices (realistic job information, job analysis, work family balance, career development, compensation and supervisor support) and their likely impact on the Marketing Executive Intention to Leave (MEIL) in the Sri Lankan leasing companies. The objective of this study was to examine the effects of HR practices on MEIL in leasing companies in Sri Lanka. The sample consisted of hundred marketing executives working for 10 different leasing companies in Sri Lanka. The data were gathered by administering questionnaires. The results indicated that five HR practices variables were negatively and considerably correlated with MEIL. The work family balance was not negatively correlated with MEIL. Results of re-grassing the HR practices on MEIL showed that compensation and job analysis were strong predictors of MEIL.

Yasir,ZeeshanShaukat, SherazAlvi, Ayesha, (2011) worked on HRM Practices& its effect on employees performance related to textile sector of Pakistan. The study was done by developing and testing the model based on human resource practices including recruitment and selection, training and performance appraisal as independent variables on the employee's performance as a dependent variable. Questionnaires and cover letters were used to collect the data through different textile mills. Research findings proved significant relationship of Human Resource Management practices and employees performance.

ZulfqarBowra, Bilal, Affan, KabirNiazi, (2012)attempted the study to examine the nature of relationship between the employee perceived performance and human resource (HR) practices (compensation, performance evaluation, and promotion practices) in the banking sector of Pakistan. 235 questionnaires were given to banking personnel through personally administrated

questionnaire to investigate about the study. The relationship and nature of relationship was calculated by applying the Spearman's correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis. The Spearman's correlation results demonstrate that, the employee perceived performance and HR practices has the positive and significant relationship. The regression results indicate that the two HR practices: performance evaluation and promotion practices were significant but the compensation practices were not significant. Moreover, management has to design their HR related polices to attain high employee performance.

ThanujaRathnaweera (2010) worked on a study to examine the impact of Human Resource Management practices on outcomes in public sector banks in Sri Lanka. The basic objective of study was to evaluate that Do HRM practices was having impact on Employee's Performance, Commitment or Retention. Methodology includes structured questionnaires to collect the data which consisted of sample of 209 employees. Multiple Regressions, Cronbachalpha, Pearson correlation coefficient and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. The findings of the research discovered that Human Resource Management practices were significant predictors of employee satisfaction, commitment and retention.

Mark A Huselid studied on a problem that was the impact of Human Resource Management on Turnover, Productivity and Corporate Financial Performance. The basic objective of the study was to find out the relationship between systems of High Performance work practices and firm performance. Data was collected through questionnaire and 968 responses were received out of 3,452. Multiple Regressions, Cronbachalpha, Pearson correlation coefficient and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. Results indicate that these practices have an economical and statistical significant impact on both intermediate employees' outcomes and short and long term measures of Corporate Financial Performance.

ALDamoe, Yazam & Kamal. (2013), worked on problem statement of Human Resource Management Practices on Organizational Performance in Libya. The aim of this study was to elaborate on the effects of HRM practices outcome on organizational performance in Libyan firm. From the literature scrutiny, this paper wraps up that HRM practices such as rewards and compensations as well as, performance appraisal were the HRM practices that improve organizational performance within the organization

ABANG OTHMAN, (2009) the purpose of this paper was to examine human resource management functions of recruitment/selection and training/development in the context of two major Japanese owned multinational electronics companies in Malaysia. A mixed-methodological approach via case studies and questionnaire surveys was used for this study. Overall 29 questionnaires from the two companies were analysed. Policies of higher level management were sought regarding their role, involvement, practices and their perceptions on the value-added contributions of HR towards organizational effectiveness. Result shows that there were similarities between their practices and the tenets of traditional Japanese management system (JMS). The overall findings indicate that their recruitment/ selection and training/development practices were influenced by their JMS which encourages specific human capital creation through a well elaborated and integrated HRM practices linking towards organizational goals.

Asif Khan, Kashif, Ijaz, Safwan, Ashfaq, (2010) the purpose of research was to create a link between HR practices and job satisfaction in public and private banks in Pakistan. The data was collected from two cities of Pakistan i.e. Rawalpindi and was Islamabad and a sample of 400 responses were collected out of 550. Different statistical tools were used in order to analyse the

data which includes T-test, frequency distribution etc. The study finds that employee selection; employee training and development and work design was having positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and employee retention.

Wright, Kehoe, (2007). This paper examines newer conceptualizations of HRM practices in the HR-Performance Relationship as well as newer conceptualizations of commitment. Methodology includes use of different statistical tools. Juxtaposing these categories of HR practices and types of commitment provides a clearer theoretical rationale for at least some ways that HR practices can influence organizational performance, be that positive or negative.

Methodology

In this study a random sampling technique was used. In the first stage a simple random sample of 2 public and 2 private banks of Pakistan was selected for data collection. The list of all these banks specified in Appendix 1. Data was collected through questionnaires. In the second stage, random sampling was used for selecting the employees from the sample banks. The reason for preferring random sampling technique was that it gives equal chance to employees working in these four banks and also helpful in generalization of the results of sample back to population. The collection of data from the sample banks were done in a research survey through a personally administered questionnaire. 105 questionnaires were distributed to the employees of randomly selected 2 public and 2 private banks of Pakistan and received 100 completed questionnaires out of 105 which contain 95.24% response rate enough for empirical analysis. The reason for adopting self-administered questionnaire was that this approach has higher response rate as respondent’s queries can be solved on spot. After collecting the data from personally administered questionnaire data was entered, arranged, processed and results were generated through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 15) software. Measures include training, planning, performance appraisal, selection and recruitment and compensation. Main reason for adopting these measures was that they were well tested on internal consistency and all measures had cronbach’s alpha in the range of 0.899. The cronbach’s alpha of this study were given in the Table 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.899	55

Table 2

Experience

	Frequency	Per cent	
Valid	Less than 1 year	4	4.0
	1 to 5 Years	38	38.0
	6 to 10	28	28.0

years		
11 to 15	15	15.0
years		
16 to	15	15.0
Onwards		
Total	100	100.0

Experience table shows 5 categories in which 4 % respondents were having experience less than 1 year, 38% were in between 1 to 5 years, 28% were in between 6 to 10 years, 15% were in between 11 to 15 years and 15% were 16 to onwards years of job experience

Table 3

Gender

	Frequency	Per cent	
Valid	Male	77	77.0
	Female	23	23.0
	Total	100	100.0

In gender table, 77% respondents were male and 23% respondents were female which shows that male respondents were more in numbers than female,

Table 4

Bank name

	Frequency	Per cent	
Valid	Bank of Punjab	27	27.0
	National Bank of Pakistan	24	24.0
	Summit Bank	24	24.0
	Habib Metro Bank	25	25.0
	Total	100	100.0

In this table, there were four banks; Bank of Punjab, National Bank of Pakistan (**Government Banks**) and Summit Bank, Habib Metro Bank (**Private Banks**). The result shows that 27% of respondents were from Bank of Punjab, 24% were from National Bank of Pakistan, 24 % were from Summit Bank, 25% were from Habib Metro Bank

Table 5

Age			
	Frequency	Per cent	
Valid	21-34	59	59.0
	35-44	23	23.0
	45-54	17	17.0
	55 or Older	1	1.0
	Total	100	100.0

Table 5 shows that there were four categories in which the ages were divided; 21 – 34, 35 – 44, 45 – 54, 55 or older. The result shows that 59% respondents were in between 21 – 34 category age, 23% were in between 35 – 44, 17% were in between 45 – 54, and 1% was 55 or older category of ages

Table 6

Education			
	Frequency	Per cent	
Valid	Bachelors	16	16.0
	Masters	79	79.0
	M.Phil.	1	1.0
	More than that	4	4.0
	Total	100	100.0

Table 6 shows the education of respondent’s i.e., Bachelors, Masters, and M.Phil. or more than that. Result shows that 16% of respondents were Bachelors, 79% were Masters, and 1% was M.Phil. And 4% were more than that.

Discussion

Human resource management has gained more devotion from corporate or private sector than from government or public sector particularly banking sector. However, to accomplish organizational goals and boost employees’ performance, effective management of HRs is equally important in any type of sector. New technologies and other resources alone can do very little to enhance the organizational performance unless the necessary HRP’s are in order. For this reason, banks need to carefully assess their existing HRP’s and perform these practices effectively.

It is more important to perform HRP’s effectively in organizations because as described by Robbins and Coulter (2006), if an organization does not take its HRM responsibilities seriously, employees’ work performance and organizational goals accomplishment may suffer. It is also claimed that poorly designed and executed HRP’s can cast adverse effects on the overall performance of any organization (Pucik, 1988). This may lead to dissatisfaction of the employees and may ultimately demoralize them. They may look for alternative means of employment. In the same way, effective

execution of HRPs is obligatory to achieve the organizational goals and to enhance overall performance of the organization (Audretsch & Thurik, 2001; Bowen & Ostroff, 2004; Gelade & Ivery, 2003; Ostroff & Bowen, 2000). This leads to energizing the employees and heightening their morale and motivation.

Findings

The variable training in this study shows that '6 to 10 years' of experience gets more training in their institutions, 'Male' respondents are more in numbers, 'Bank of Punjab' employees gets more training as compared to others, 21 – 44 years of age employees gets more training rather than other and those respondents who has got 'Master's Degree gets more Training.

Result shows that respondents who are in the category 'Less than 1 year' are more involved in planning session, Both 'Male' and 'Female' are equally involved in planning session, 'Habib Metro Bank' employees are more involved in planning session, respondent whose age is in the category of '55 or Above' gets themselves more involved in planning discussions and all the categories of Education i.e. (Bachelors, Masters, M.Phil., More than that) are equally involved in planning session of their institutions.

Performance Appraisal shows that those respondents who are in the category of experience '16 to onwards' are more in numbers who gets performance appraisal more than others, gender wise 'Male' respondents are more in numbers who gets more performance appraisal from their organizations, 'Summit Bank and Habib Metro Bank' (Private Banks) provides their employees more performance appraisal as compared to other 'National Bank of Pakistan and Bank of Punjab' (Governments Banks), Age in the category of 45 – 55 onwards are more satisfied in getting performance appraisal as compared to others and those respondents who hold 'Masters' degree are more satisfied about their performance appraisal.

Selection process are more satisfied who are having experience 'Less than 1 year' are more satisfied about selection process in their organizations, Gender wise both 'Male' and 'Female' respondents are equally satisfied, Selection process in 'National Bank of Pakistan' is much better than other banks, Age wise all respondents are equally satisfied about selection process and those respondents who are having 'Bachelors' and 'Masters' degree are more satisfied about selection process.

In recruitment process, those respondents who are having 'Less than 1 years' of experience are more satisfied as compared to other, Gender wise 'Female' respondents are much satisfied about recruitment process in their organizations, Respondents of 'National Bank of Pakistan' is more satisfied about recruitment process and those respondents whose education 'M.Phil.' are more satisfied about recruitment process in their organizations.

Compensation policy shows that those respondents whose job experience is in the category of '16 to onwards' are more satisfied about their compensation policy, If we look gender wise 'Female' respondents are comparatively more satisfied about their organization compensation policies, 'National Bank of Pakistan' is having much better policies about compensation of their employees, Those respondents age wise who are in the category of '55 or older' are more satisfied, and those respondents who hold 'Masters' degree are much satisfied about compensation policy.

Conclusion

This study is designed to investigate the impact of Human Resource Management practices on the performance of the employees. To find out the performance determinants research model of HRM practices was used. There are many HR practices like recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, career path, compensation, job definition. Only three practices (recruitment and selection, planning, training, compensation, performance appraisal) were taken to understand the impact on the performance of the employees. These factors were taken because of their ultimate requirement of any banking sector. This is the interesting study proving the importance of those practices which highly affects the performance of the employees. This study will provide an insight in the banking sector that what makes an employee to perform better. All variables (recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, compensation) are found to be significantly related with performance of employees. So we conclude that recruitment and selection, compensation and performance appraisal play a vital role for the performance of the employees as training of the employees is also important but there is something other is more important to work on. All HRM practices should be used to understand their impact on the performance of the employees.

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